

The role of celebrity endorsement on purchase intention of ERIGO products

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Abstract

This research was conducted to see how celebrities as trusted endorsers can influence consumer purchase intentions and boost sales. In addition, to find out the involvement of celebrity endorsements in encouraging consumers of the Erigo brand which has become a well-known local brand in Indonesia. This study aims to determine the factors that influence purchase intentions for Erigo products. Data were analyzed using PLS-SEM and with a total of 377 respondents spread across Indonesia. The results of this study indicate that celebrity endorsement, brand attitude, and brand loyalty have a positive effect on purchase intention.

Keywords: Celebrity endorsement; Brand attitude; Brand loyalty; Purchase intention

1. Introduction

The rapid development of information technology allows consumers to easily find information about the whereabouts of a product. Under these conditions, companies are required to be responsive to consumer desires and provide clear information about their products to get positive responses from consumers [1]. In the shift in people's culture due to the development of information technology, industry players must respond quickly, including the advertising industry. One of the marketing strategies carried out by companies so that their products can win the market and attract the attention of consumers is an advertising strategy [2]. Introducing products using Celebrity Endorsement as an icon can increase Purchase Intention. The selected celebrity must be able to represent the character of the product being advertised [3]. Celebrity endorsers influence products and services backed by talent, attractiveness, and trustworthiness. Effectively celebrities are mostly used to support the success of a brand [4]. The phenomenon that shows celebrity endorsers as supporters in promotional activities has been going on for a long time. This is because celebrity users as endorsers are believed to influence consumer purchase intentions and boost product sales [5]. Osei-Frimpong et al. (2019) emphasized that the dimensions that form celebrity credibility include attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise. In Indonesia, it can be seen that there are many famous local products. One of them is local products in the field of clothing such as local t-shirts. Erigo is one of the biggest local *fashion brands* in Indonesia [7]. In September 2021, the local *fashion world* was shocked when Erigo appeared at New York Fashion Week (NYFW) 2021. Erigo's DNA brand, as a local brand that sells casual products, was increasingly formed after deciding to use a casual fashion theme.

2. Literature review

2.1. Cognitive Psychological Theory

This study uses a cognitive psychological theory model as its main foundation. According to this theory, there are several consumers in obtaining a brand or product consisting of several mental processes that must be passed. This stage begins with gathering information and knowledge related to the product, after they receive an evaluation regarding the

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product, feelings of liking or disliking the product or brand will emerge and then encourage purchase intentions. Consumer attitudes toward brands will be measured in research [8]. Beliefs that exist in consumers include liking, choosing, and believing [9]. Someone's opinion that is formed based on belief will be difficult to change, retailers need to create confidence in the target of their marketing mix, namely consumers in achieving their goals. The concept of brand attitude toward a product is examined to determine the impact it has on their purchase intention. Cognitive theory is a process that involves aspects of knowledge, reasoning, or thought. The consumer's mind will receive information about products, brands, and so on, which will then be processed by the human brain. In this cognitive domain, information from online marketing will improve knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, and consumer evaluation of a product [10].

2.2. Celebrity Endorsements

The definition of celebrity endorsement is an agreement between an individual who enjoys public recognition (a celebrity) and an entity (for example, a brand) to use a celebrity to promote the entity to expand its scope by leveraging the fame of the individual being utilized. To further explain the different ways in which fame, or capital, individuals can leverage today [11]. In the field of marketing, it shows that choosing an endorser that is by the program or product being promoted is very important, taking into account the profile of an endorser who can attract the attention of the audience and transfer the image to the audience through the message he wants to convey [12]. Increased competition has encouraged marketers to use celebrity endorsements which create attention to help market products. Wang et al. (2017), there are three supporting components of celebrity endorsement as follows:

- Trustworthiness refers to the honesty, integrity, and trust of an endorser which can influence consumer perceptions. Advertisers capitalize on the value of trust by selecting endorsers who are widely perceived as honest, trustworthy, and reliable because consumers view untrustworthy celebrity endorsers, regardless of their other qualities, as a source of questionable messages.
- Expertise is defined as the extent to which a communicator is considered a valid source of statements. This refers to the knowledge, experience, or skills possessed by an endorser. It doesn't matter whether an endorser is an expert what matters is how the target audience perceives the endorser. More skilled celebrities are more persuasive to generate more intent to buy the brand.
- Attractiveness defined as the attractiveness of an endorser plays an important role because some statistically significant individuals assess the endorser as having high attractiveness which can influence consumers' purchase intentions towards the brand.

2.3. Brand Attitudes

Brand attitude is a determinant for consumers to evaluate and choose a brand. A buying behavior can be predicted through the attitude of the brand. Attitudes toward luxury brands are opportunities to strengthen luxury brands and gain a competitive advantage [14]. Brand attitude is a variable to predict consumer brand choice. Brand attitude is knowledge about the functional and symbolic attributes of the brand formed by consumers. This knowledge is obtained through the physical experience of a product or marketing content. Social media marketing activities can influence brand attitudes [15]. *Brand attitude* is an overall evaluation of a brand, in which consumers believe in the extent to which the brand of a product has certain advantages. Besides that, it can be interpreted as well as an assessment of how good or bad a product is if it has these advantages and attributes.

2.4. Brand Loyalty

Brand Loyalty (brand loyalty) includes behavioral loyalty, namely consumers repeatedly buying a brand, and attitudinal loyalty, namely brand preferences that reflect the emotional relationship between consumers and brands. Unique, memorable, and reinforcing experiences build brand loyalty and create strong emotional bonds with brands. The positive influence of loyal customers on brands in today's competitive market, under conditions where the cost of acquiring new customers is higher than retaining current customers gradually, increases the significance of customer loyalty (Bilgin, 2018). Consumers who have strong beliefs about the brand will form brand loyalty [17].

2.5. Purchase Intentions

Product purchase decision-making is essentially driven by consumer purchase intentions (purchase intention). Consumers have an intention to buy a particular product because they have evaluated the information collected. The purchase intention process begins when the consumer evaluates the product. Consumers evaluate by seeking information from outsiders and personal experience [18]. Purchase intention is the willingness of consumers to consider purchases and commitments to make purchases in the future [5]. Purchase intention is a motivational state in

consumers that is considered a consequence of perceived value [14]. Consumer purchase intention for luxury products has several motives such as satisfying oneself and others, personal aspects, and the value of luxury brands [19].

3. Hypothesis Development

3.1. The Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Brand Attitude

Celebrity endorsements are considered to have three main points, namely trustworthiness, expertise, and attractiveness. Consumer trust is described as a value summary that creates positive features and increases message acceptance. Trust is the most useful and effective tool to make customers more confident and reliable in brands. The more persuasive a celebrity's expertise is, the more purchasing decisions will be generated because celebrities are perceived as experts in a particular area, resulting in higher brand endorsements than celebrities with no skills. A celebrity is attractive because he has built a popular image among the public. Its appeal increases the persuasive power of customers because they want to be like the celebrity they love. This research is supported by [20] who state that celebrity endorsements which are supported by 3 dimensions have a significant influence on brand attitude. The study of the relationship between Celebrity Endorsement and Brand Attitude found that respondents' attitudes toward Celebrity Endorsement had a positive effect on Brand Attitude [21]. Research Xu & Pratt (2018), states that congruence between celebrities and products is an important factor in determining the effectiveness of celebrity endorsements. Previous literature said that there is a positive relationship between celebrity endorsements and brand attitudes. A brand transfers its identity to others too, they evaluate others based on their consumption behavior. Therefore, the image conveyed by the brand is very important. So that the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H1: Effect of Celebrity Endorsement on Brand Attitude

3.2. Celebrity Endorsement for Loyalty

Celebrity endorsers play a role in making consumers less price sensitive and more loyal to products or brands, consumers who see celebrity endorsers as their role models will most likely stick to the same brands endorsed by these celebrities. Therefore, in research celebrities can be considered to have the ability to influence consumer repurchasing behavior, namely making them loyal to brands [23]. The existence of this celebrity has a strong influence on consumer behavior. The effect of symbolic communication between consumers and products can be conveyed optimally if the characteristics of the endorser and the product match. This will encourage consumer behavior, one of which is loyalty. This provides information that there is a significant influence between celebrity endorsements according to the product on loyalty [24]. However, this study shows that several dimensions of celebrity endorsement are measured as partially insignificant such as attractiveness and multiplicity [25] So that the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H2: Effect of Celebrity Endorsement on Loyalty

3.3. Effect of Brand Attitude on Purchase Intention

Brand attitudes develop from brand exposure which is knowledge related to the functional and symbolic attributes of a brand formed by consumers through a marketing experience. Brand attitude has a positive influence on purchase intention [15]. Attitude is the main determinant in carrying out certain behaviors. Individual social behavior is motivated by attitude towards the behavior. Individuals involved with the product have a strong attitude. This results in forming the intention of the attitude. In line with previous research, the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention is positive and significant. The more positive the brand attitude is, the more likely it is to buy the product [26]. Other studies explain that consumer attitudes toward a brand have a positive relationship with purchase intentions and readiness to pay for them. The brand attitude becomes intentional behavior in consumers. Factors such as brand awareness and consumer perceptions can, directly and indirectly, influence consumer purchase intentions. The results of this study indicate that brand attitudes influence consumer purchase intentions [27]. The description of previous research [15], [26], [27] regarding the influence of *brand attitude* on *purchase intention* influences these two variables. A strong attitude possessed by consumers will increase the intention to buy. So that the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H3: Effect of brand attitude on purchase intention

3.4. Effect of Celebrity Endorsement on Purchase Intention

Almohaimmeed (2019), brand loyalty is influenced by the credibility and perceived quality of brands that are promoted using celebrity endorsements to influence consumer intentions to buy or repurchase, recommendations to others,

willingness to pay more, and reduction of complaints. Consumers generally have higher purchase intentions with familiar brands. Osei-Frimpong et al (2019), argue that brands with high awareness and a good image can promote brand loyalty, which in turn can lead to increased consumer purchase intentions. In addition, brand equity tends to influence consumer buying behavior. When someone buys a product and has a brand name, it means that the consumer has awareness of that brand. Through the description of previous research, brand loyalty is said to be the ability of consumers to continue to use the brands offered and is a measure of consumer attachment to a particular brand with positive and consistent thoughts to make purchases in the future [6], [28], [29]. So that conclusions can be drawn regarding the influence of brand loyalty on Purchase Intention the hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H4: Effect of brand loyalty on Purchase Intention

3.5. Effect of Celebrity Endorsement on Purchase Intention

Celebrity endorsements are commonly used advertisements that are directly linked to the advertised product. Previous research, explains that the credibility of celebrity endorsers has a significant influence on the formation of purchase intentions [30]. The use of celebrity endorsers is one of the factors considered by respondents to believe in the truth of the contents of the message conveyed by advertisers. As an attention-grabbing figure in advertising is one way of conveying a message. The more famous the celebrity who becomes the advertising model can encourage consumers to desire to buy products supported by the celebrity [31]. Other research also states that the use of celebrities with the attributes of their attractiveness, trust, and expertise can influence consumers' purchase intentions for a product. Celebrity endorser support helps consumers to relate more to celebrities and can assist in developing a positive attitude towards the brand to increase purchase intention. This is based on stimulating the purchase intention of consumers to offer creativity so that it is unique compared to others. In delivery, it must be clear and directed so that it can encourage the attractiveness of the product [6]. Through the description of previous research which are related to the influence of celebrity endorsement on purchase intention, the better advertisement delivered by a celebrity endorser on a product, the better can encourage consumer purchase intentions. So the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H5: Effect of celebrity endorsement on purchase intention

4. Research framework

This study focuses on consumer attitudes and purchase intentions by examining the relationship and influence of celebrity endorsements, brand attitudes, and brand loyalty. This model was adopted in previous research and is expected to contribute and see how celebrity endorsements influence the current digitalization era. The model in this study identifies four variables in determining the variables that drive consumer purchase intentions. There are independent variables namely Celebrity Endorsement, Brand Attitude, and Brand Loyalty. And the dependent variable is Purchase Intention.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

5. Methodology

In this research, the object chosen is social media users in Indonesia who will buy Erigo products. In this study, a quantitative approach was used. The survey was distributed via Whatsapp and Instagram online. In the research, the object chosen is people who will buy Erigo products or more than some factors cause a problem. This approach is taken to state that the X variable causes the Y variable. So if the X variable is removed or changed in a certain way the Y problem can be solved [32]. X or independent variables include *Celebrity Endorsement*, *Brand Loyalty*, and *Brand Attitude*. The Y or dependent variable is *purchase intention*. According to the time dimension, researchers use *cross-sectional studies* to collect data at one time or only once collected in a certain period [33]. The sample size of the study

refers to Hair et al. (2017), which explains that the ideal sample size is determined by multiplying the number of indicators in 5-10 studies. The questionnaire in this study consisted of 23 statements, which were measured with a Likert scale of 1 (Strongly Disagree) – 5 (Strongly Agree). The variables Consumer Perception of Quality, Celebrity Endorsement, Brand Loyalty and Purchase Intention adopt the measurement developed [6]. Brand Attitude adopted by Wang et al. (2017).

Table 1 shows the test criteria in this study through the results of the PIs Algorithm output. Meanwhile, Bootstrapping is used in this study to process SEM in the level of variable influence. The hypothesis can be declared significant if it has a p-value of 0.05. This can be explained that there influence of the independent variable on the dependent.

Table 1 Test Criteria

Type	Index	Criteria	Source
Validity and Reliability Test	Loading Factor	>0.70	Hartono (2011)
	Composite Reliability	> 0.70	
	Convergent Validity	AVE > 0.5	
	Discriminant Validity	AVE > correlation between constructs	Ghozali and Laten (2015)
Hypothesis Measurement	Statistical Significance	P-Value < 0.50 (Bootstrap)	Hartono (2011)
Structural Models	Collinearity (VIF)	< 0.5	Yamin (2021)
	R-Square	0.67 (High) 0.33 (Moderate) 0.19 (Weak)	

6. Results and discussion

6.1. Respondents

In this study, 377 respondents were willing to fill out a survey through social media who were interested in buying Erigo. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of people's attitudes on the intention to buy Erigo products. According to the characteristics of the respondents, those who are willing to fill out the questionnaire have the intention to buy goods throughout Indonesia. These characteristics include

Table 2 Classification of Respondents

Age group	Frequency
Less than 25 years	289
25-35 years	78
35-45 years	5
Over 45 years	5
Total	377
Gender	Frequency
Woman	245
Man	132
Total	377
Monthly Income	Frequency
Less than IDR 2,500,000 or USD 168	259

IDR 2,500,000- IDR 5,000,000 or USD 168-USD 336	77
IDR 5,000,000- IDR 7,500,000 or USD 336-USD 504	27
IDR 7,500,000- IDR 10,000,000 or USD 504-USD 672	6
More than IDR 10,000,000 or USD 672	8
Total	377

6.2. Measurement Models

In this study, the evaluation of the reflective measurement model consisted of testing the validity and reliability of indicators for each construct. Types of construct validity include convergent and discriminant validity. The reliability test includes the composite reliability test and Cornbach's alpha. Table 4 shows the results of calculating convergent validity data for each construct.

Table 4 Convergent Validity

Items	Brand Attitudes	Brand Loyalty	Celebrity Endorsements	Purchase Intentions
AT01			0.729	
AT02			0.724	
AT03			0.725	
BA01	0.915			
BA02	0.890			
BA03	0.795			
BL01		0.933		
BL02		0.951		
BL03		0.905		
EX01			0.742	
EX02			0.811	
EX03			0.789	
EX04			0.816	
PI01				0.799
PI02				0.855
PI03				0.844
PI04				0.877
PI05				0.771
PI06				0.871
TW01			0.748	
TW02			0.802	
TW03			0.751	
TW04			0.763	

Loading Factor is used to assess convergent validity. The criterion used is 0.70. These findings indicate that the overall value of the loading factor in each construct is greater than 0.7. As a result, the indicators used in this study for measurement are said to be valid and able to represent each latent variable. In Table 5, the square root of the AVE

calculated by going through each latent variable has a greater value than the correlation value between the latent variable and the other latent variables. This indicates that discriminant validity is met. Furthermore, variables can be used to describe something different from one another.

Table 5 Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Factors	Brand Attitudes	Brand Loyalty	Celebrity Endorsements	Purchase Intentions
Brand Attitudes	0.868			
Brand Loyalty	0.746	0.930		
Celebrity Endorsements	0.554	0.530	0.764	
Purchase Intentions	0.803	0.824	0.669	0.837

Data from Table 6 shows that the overall value of Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and AVE exceeds the recommended threshold and AVE on validity is met. The results of the reliability test through Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, have met the criteria indicating that all variables are reliable and can be evaluated further.

Table 6 Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, AVE

Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Brand Attitudes	0.835	0.902	0.754
Brand Loyalty	0.921	0.950	0.864
Celebrity Endorsements	0.929	0.939	0.584
Purchase Intentions	0.914	0.933	0.701

Based on Table 7, these indicators generally do not show multicollinearity. This is evidenced by the VIF value of each variable which is less than 5. Based on the test results, the indicators in this study were maintained because there were no indications that did not match the criteria used.

Table 7 Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

Items	VIF
AT01	2,206
AT02	2,452
AT03	2,090
BA03	2,912
BA 01	2,580
BA02	1,549
BA03	3,894
BL01	4,641
BL02	2,785
BL03	2,517
EX02	2,955
EX03	2,772
EX04	2,980
PI01	2,566

PI02	3,043
PI03	3,860
PI04	4,476
PI05	2010
PI06	2,915
TW01	2,286
TW02	2,883
TW03	2,363
TW04	2,605

6.3. Structural Model and Hypothesis Testing

The results of the model measurements are shown in Figure 2. After the estimated model meets the criteria for convergent and discriminant validity, the next step is to test the structural model. Evaluation of the structural model can be done by looking at the coefficient of determination or R-Square. The R square value for Purchase Intention is 0.800 which explains the combined effect of Celebrity Endorsement, Brand Attitude, and Brand Loyalty on Purchase Intention is 80% and the remaining 20% is influenced by other variables.

Hypothesis testing tests the significance of the path coefficient, showing the effect of the independent variables on the related variables. Path coefficients were obtained by testing using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with bootstrapping. We used a 95% level and a standard error of 5%, or a P-Value of 0.05, in this test of significance. If the results have a p-value <0.05, then the hypothesis is said to be significant or H_a is accepted. However, if the p-value is greater than 0.05, then the hypothesis is said to be insignificant or H_a is rejected.

Figure 2 Inside Model Measurement

Table 8 Hypothesis Testing

Interactions	Path Coefficients	Sample Means (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Brand Attitude →Purchase Intention	0.335	0.338	0.053	6,344	0.000
Brand Loyalty →Purchase Intention	0.442	0.434	0.052	8,488	0.000
Celebrity Endorsement →Brand Attitude	0.554	0.560	0.052	10,642	0.000
Celebrity Endorsement →Brand Loyalty	0.536	0.536	0.051	10.317	0.000
Celebrity Endorsement →Purchase Intention	0.253	0.253	0.051	6.109	

Based on the data in Table 8, it shows that Hypothesis 1 (H1), namely celebrity endorsement, has a p-value of 0.000. This value shows less than 0.05 which can be explained that the two variables have an influence. The path coefficient value of 0.554 can be explained that these two variables have an influence. Celebrity endorsements are considered to have three main points, namely trustworthiness, expertise, and attractiveness. This research is supported by [20] who state that celebrity endorsements which are supported by 3 dimensions have a significant influence on brand attitude. The use of celebrity endorsers must go through several considerations, including the level of celebrity popularity with the problem of whether the chosen celebrity can represent the character of the product being advertised. Celebrities must be able to provide information about brands and product attributes that are fun, convincing, and attract the attention of the general public. It is felt that it is easier to use celebrities as endorsers to influence the psychology of consumer consumption. The use of celebrities in an advertisement involves attractiveness and credibility which is its uniqueness.

Hypothesis 2 (H2) can be concluded that it has a significant effect. The p-value on H2 is 0.000 which means less than 0.05 so it can be stated that Celebrity Endorsement affects loyalty. Besides that, the direction of the relationship is positive when the celebrity endorsement gets positive support, it can increase consumer loyalty to a brand. Customer loyalty is a deep commitment from consumers to repurchase. It results in purchasing the same brand despite situational influences and marketing efforts that create the potential for switching. The use of celebrities attracts consumers to the product. The figure of an artist using a certain item has the charm and trust or expertise that is recognized by the public. Therefore, the selection of celebrities along with a product has succeeded in shaping public perceptions to continue to want to buy products and create loyalty.

The results of hypothesis 3 (H3) explain the relationship between brand attitude and purchase intention with a p-value of 0.000. This value shows less than 0.05, it can be explained that the two variables have an influence. The path coefficient value is 0.335 which shows that there is a positive influence of brand attitude on purchase intention. This shows that the higher the brand attitude towards someone, the higher the purchase intention. So it can be concluded that. This shows that brand attitudes have a very important role in increasing consumer decisions to make the products offered trusted products.

Hypothesis 4 and Hypothesis 5 show a p-value below 0.000 so they are declared influential and significant. When the aspect of brand loyalty and the influence of celebrity endorsement is good, it also has a positive influence and increases the aspect of purchase intention. H4 shows that there is an effect of brand loyalty on purchase intention. These results explain that the perceived quality of consumers is loyalty to a product in making purchases. High *brand loyalty* indicates that a *brand* and consumer relationship is getting stronger and results in a consumer being motivated or interested in making decisions in purchasing a *brand*. Hypothesis 5 is accepted which shows celebrity endorsement influences purchase intention. These results indicate the influence of the celebrity endorsement variable on purchase intention. This explains that celebrities can support the psychological side of consumers which can influence the attitudes and beliefs of consumers in making purchases.

7. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis conducted in this study, it can be concluded that *brand attitude*, *brand loyalty*, and *celebrity endorsement* influence *customer purchase intention*. Besides that, the *celebrity endorsement* variable also influences brand loyalty and brand attitude. For researchers who are going to do a similar topic, it is advisable to research by using or adding other factors outside of the factors that have been studied by previous researchers, adding to the number of research samples. In addition, it is also advisable to extend the research period and use other analytical tools, to obtain better results

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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